

bond with n -electron lowers the frequency of the n -orbital by an amount equal to the energy of the hydrogen bond. The frequency shifts ($\Delta\nu$) observed and the energy values ($\Delta E = h\Delta\nu$) calculated are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THE FREQUENCIES OF THE CHROMOPHORE WHEN IT IS FREE AND COMPLEXED WITH BUTANOL, IN VARIOUS n -BUTANOL CARBONYL SYSTEMS

System	Free ν_f cm ⁻¹	Bonded ν_b cm ⁻¹	Blue Shift $\Delta\nu$ cm ⁻¹	ΔE Kcals/mole
n -Butanol + Acetone	35,971	36,550	579	1.65
Ethyl methyl ketone	35,971	36,364	393	1.12
Cyclohexanone	34,433	35,112	629	1.80
Acetophenone	31,368	31,746	378	1.08

Acknowledgement

One of the author (R. M.) is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Epoxidation of α,β -Unsaturated Aldehydes and Esters

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Manuscript received 8 February 1982, accepted
28 December 1982

A systematic study of the kinetics of epoxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones with alkaline hydrogen peroxide in methanol medium has been carried out recently¹ and similar studies have been extended to α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and esters. Such a study will give one an insight into the mechanism of epoxidation in non-aqueous solvents and would also permit a comparison of the reactivity of the $>C=O$ group when attached to a $>C=C<$ linkage during epoxidation. Recently, there have been reports of successful alkaline epoxidations of cinnamaldehyde, crotonaldehyde and citral under controlled pH conditions².

On the other hand the epoxidation of unsaturated esters of cinnamic and crotonic acids has been carried out with several peroxy-acids in a variety of solvents and the rates of epoxidation have been reported³. However, to this date, there has been no report in the literature on the study of the kinetics of epoxidation of α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and esters using alkaline hydrogen peroxide. Hence a systematic study of the epoxidation of these compounds has been carried out.

Experimental

Cinnamaldehyde, crotonaldehyde, citral, methyl and ethyl crotonates and methyl and ethyl cinnamates (Flüka, extra pure) were employed.

Epoxy methyl and ethyl crotonate and epoxy ethyl cinnamate were prepared⁴ and used for comparison of the R_f values (Table 1) with those of the products isolated soon after the kinetic studies. Epoxides of cinnamaldehyde and crotonaldehyde were separated by tlc and identified as their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES AT 30°
SOLVENT: BENZENE-METHYL ACETATE (2:1)

Compound	Substrate	Epoxide
Cinnamaldehyde	0.51	0.23
Crotonaldehyde	0.55	0.23
Ethyl crotonate	0.60	0.34
Methyl crotonate	0.71	0.18
Ethyl cinnamate	0.48	0.27
*Benzaldehyde	0.63	—
*Acetaldehyde	0.19	—

*Values used to check up the fission products of epoxy cinnamaldehyde and epoxy crotonaldehyde.

UV and tlc techniques have been employed for the kinetic and analytical studies. TLC has been

specially employed for the separation of liquid epoxides for analysis and identification. The general method of procedure is the same as that adopted earlier. A lower concentration (total concentration $10^{-3} M$) has been chosen for the determination of rate constants, which helped in preventing the cleavage reactions that are usually observed at higher concentrations. The results indicate that the concentration of NaOH has a significant effect on the reaction.

Results and Discussion

Values of k_2 have been presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR EPOXIDATION

[Substrate] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[H_2O_2] = [NaOH] = 2.9 \times 10^{-2} M$
Solvent: MeOH Temp. 30°

Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^2$ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
$C_6H_5CH=CHCHO$	7.74
$OH_2CH=CHCHO$	5.29
$(OH_2)_2C=CHCH_2-CH_2-C(OH_2)=CHCHO$	4.44
$CH_3CH=CHCO_2CH_3$	1.11
$OH_2CH=CHCO_2C_2H_5$	1.82
$C_6H_5CH=CHCO_2CH_3$	3.75
$C_6H_5CH=CHCO_2C_2H_5$	4.99

α,β -Unsaturated aldehydes: Cinnamaldehyde has a higher rate of epoxidation than crotonaldehyde and in the latter, the electron-donating effect of $-CH_3$ group at the β -carbon lowers the rate. This behaviour finds a parallelism in the pair citral and cinnamalacetophone, where the double bond α,β - to the carbonyl group is epoxidized readily, whereas the terminal double bond is unaffected⁶.

α,β -Unsaturated esters: Compared to aldehydes and ketones the esters have generally lower rate of epoxidation. Esters of cinnamic acid have higher (nearly twice) rates than the esters of crotonic acid.

The ability to add peroxy acids is so low in the esters that only the most reactive of them are able to oxidise the double bond. The rate constants depend on the peroxy acid employed and the solvent used⁴. Again, epoxidation is rapid in non-ionizing solvents and there is little or no salt effect or catalysis by acids. It was therefore assumed that ionic species or ionic transition states were not involved. This is in contrast with the present work on the epoxidation by alkaline hydrogen peroxide.

The reactivity of $>C=C<$ in aldehydes, ketones and esters depends essentially on the nature of the groups linked with it. It is known that of all the carbonyl compounds the most reactive are aldehydes, while the ketones are less reactive. As to the carbonyl group in esters it bears little resemblance in properties to the carbonyl group of aldehydes and ketones. The reactivity of the carbonyl group must depend largely on the magnitude of the positive charge on the carbonyl carbon

atom. The larger this positive charge, the more readily the addition of the nucleophilic reagent takes place. The gradual decrease in reactivity of the carbonyl group in aldehydes, ketones, and esters observed during the epoxidation by alkaline H_2O_2 is thus a direct indication that the reaction is a nucleophilic addition reaction across an ethylenic bond.

$k_2 \times 10^2$ lit. mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ at 30° : $C_6H_5CH=CHCHO$ 7.74

$C_6H_5CH=CHCO_2C_2H_5$ 6.22
 $C_6H_5CH=CHCO_2CH_3$ 3.75

Therefore, the tendency of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds to undergo nucleophilic addition indicates that the magnitude of the charge on the β -carbon atom is the dominant factor controlling the epoxidation by alkaline H_2O_2 . The results are consistent with the conclusions that electron-releasing groups attached to the β -carbon atom in the olefin diminish the rate of epoxidation and electron-attracting groups enhance it.

Mechanism of epoxidation: The foregoing data indicate that the epoxidation proceeds by the slow initial attack of HO_2^- anion on the β -carbon atom followed by ring closure and elimination of OH^- anion from the adduct as postulated for α,β -unsaturated ketones¹.

Reactions of this type are of Michael Claisen which involve the attack of a nucleophilic reagent on $>C=C<$ system conjugated to an unsaturated electron-attracting group. Stereochemical studies also support this mechanism⁶. The reaction is limited to attack at the β -carbon atom and does not involve a competing reaction at the carbonyl carbon atom such as occurring in the addition of a Grignard reagent. As a result of alkaline hydrogen peroxide-epoxidation cleavage, the corresponding aldehydes (benzaldehyde or acetaldehyde) were always identified as one of the reaction products. The oxidative-cleavage mechanism indicated that it always proceeds by the slow initial attack of HO_2^- anion on the α -carbon atom (unlike epoxidation) followed by the rupture of C—O bond as shown for the ketones.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Dr. Sp. Shanmuganathan, Head of the Department of Chemistry for facilities and the U. G. C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Anomalous Transport Behaviour During Electrolysis

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Manuscript received 10 March 1980, revised 11 November 1980,
accepted 12 November 1982

WHEN a solution of a salt such as sodium sulphate is electrolysed, equivalent amounts of alkali and acid as expected get liberated at the cathode and the anode respectively, each being also equivalent to the current passed. We checked it up and found it to be true at room temperature and nearabout. However, at a higher temperature of about 40° onwards the results are totally unexpected and this is reported in this note.

Experimental

The electrolysis cell is a simple U-tube (30 cm high, 32 mm O.D.) immersed in a thermostat with arrangements for draining out liquid from different levels on one side, the other side being then kept stoppered. The electrodes are platinum foils (1 cm × 1 cm) or platinum wires (1 cm) inserted from the top. The electrolytes are either sodium or potassium sulphate solutions of varying strengths ($10^{-2} N$ to N). We passed 10 mA current through the electrodes for about 2 hr and drew off the cathode solution and titrated it. We verified that chemical changes take place under this condition upto a depth of about 6 to 8 inches or so from the top to a gradually decreasing extent.

Results and Discussion

The results are presented graphically in Fig. 1. The most striking observation is that with an increase in temperature the alkali liberated decreases very considerably, so much so that at 60° it is ~5% of the expected amount. The alkali liberated at the cathode at room temperature is almost equal to the theoretical amount, but it falls far short of the theoretical value at 40° and more so at 60°. This sharp change with temperature can be convincingly demonstrated, though in a qualitative manner by removing from time to time a little solution with a dropper from near the cathode and testing it against phenolphthalein or a universal indicator in an experiment similar to the "polarity test". At room temperature a positive test is obtained within

Fig. 1

0.5 min whereas at 60° there is hardly any positive response even after 10 min. With a similar cell but with arrangement for separate collection of the cathode gas and the anode gas¹ we verified that these gases are explosive mixtures in agreement with previous report² from this laboratory. However, the total volume shows a considerable deficit at room temperature but the deficit gets almost wiped out at the higher temperature.

Theory: This surprising result is difficult to understand against the well-accepted Hittorf idea of ion migration. The solution contains Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions to an extent about a million times that of the H^+ and OH^- ions. If we imagine a partition at the middle, any movement of Na^+ ions and SO_4^{2-} ions across this partition should lead to liberation of acid and alkali. Since the acid-alkali liberation is observed to be very much inhibited, the compelling conclusion appears to be that the current conduction is predominantly not through Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions under this condition. The alternative idea of electronic conduction cannot be true because in that case there will be no gas liberation to a proportionate extent. Actually gases get amply liberated both at the cathode and at the anode. Both the gases are highly explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen and the total amount is only slightly less than that prescribed by Faraday's law. The real problem is to find a mechanism which is not accompanied by chemical decomposition but allows for gas liberation (even mixtures) at the two electrodes. We believe that charged clusters of water molecules, $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_x^+$ at the anode and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_y^-$ at the cathode, form and these species take more and more part in current conduction with increase in temperature. These species break down after moving for some distance, liberating oxygen and hydrogen respectively ($\text{H}_2\text{O}^- = \text{H} + \text{OH}^-$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ = \text{H}^+ + \text{OH}$). When such decomposition of H_2O^- takes place in the